

Methods of Agriculture in the *Rgveda* and their Modern Relevance

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Agriculture and allied activities have been providing subsistence for most of the population, since the ancient period. Agriculturists in ancient India were quite aware of the nature of soil and its relations to the production of a particular crop of economic importance. The Vedas are the main source of information regarding agricultural activities practiced by the Aryans. The Vedas attach great importance to agriculture. Among the ancient Vedic treatises mainly the *Rgveda* records various aspects of agriculture. In the *Rgveda*, the gambler is advised to stop gambling and engage himself in agriculture to improve his condition. The *ŚatapathaBrāhma* has mentioned the four principal operations of agriculture. They are ploughing, sowing, reaping and threshing.

It seems indigenous methods of agriculture of ancient India are more relevant for present day methods. Ancient farmers used organic materials for nourishment and protection of crops. This ancient practice is still followed by our modern farmers as they also move towards organic farming instead of depending on chemicals. It is observed that ancient farmers had adequate knowledge on meteorology along with the geographical and climatic conditions. The indigenous method of weather forecasting is still followed by our modern farmers in India. Even today the village farmers who have also knowledge in astrology can predict about the weather accurately by following Almanac. Thus, this paper is a modest attempt to find out the traditional methods of agriculture in the *Rgveda* and their modern relevance.

Keywords: Vedic literature, Agriculture, Modern relevance.